

**LEXICOGRAPHIC CHALLENGES IN BILINGUAL TERMINOLOGY: A
COMPARATIVE STUDY OF LINGUISTIC TERMS IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK**

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Annotation: This study investigates the lexicographic challenges involved in the bilingual treatment of specialized linguistic terms between English and Uzbek. Focusing on comparative analysis, the research examines structural and semantic differences in how linguistic terms are defined and presented in dictionaries and academic works.

Key words: lexicography, terminology, linguistic terms, English and Uzbek language, dictionary, translation challenges, linguistic terminology.

Аннотация: В этом исследовании изучаются лексикографические проблемы, связанные с двуязычной обработкой специализированных лингвистических терминов между английским и узбекским языками. Сосредоточившись на сравнительном анализе, исследование изучает структурные и семантические различия в том, как лингвистические термины определяются и представляются в словарях и академических работах.

Ключевые слова: лексикография, терминология, лингвистические термины, английский и узбекский языки, словарь, проблемы перевода, лингвистическая терминология.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu tadqiqot ingliz va o‘zbek tillari o‘rtasidagi maxsus lingvistik atamalarning ikki tilli muomalasi bilan bog‘liq leksikografik muammolarni o‘rganadi. Qiyosiy tahlilga e‘tibor qaratgan holda, tadqiqot lug‘atlar va akademik ishlarda lingvistik atamalarning ta‘rifi va taqdim etilishidagi tarkibiy va semantik farqlarni o‘rganadi.

Kalit so‘zlar: leksikografiya, terminologiya, lingvistik atamalar, ingliz va o‘zbek tillari, lug‘at, tarjima muammolari, lingvistik terminologiya.

Nowadays, as communication and collaboration are growing dramatically, language issues continue strengthening and widening globally. In this case, there might be appeared a number of translation challenges of any terms, especially, linguistic terms which have been investigated in this work. As there is a great number of dictionaries that are specialized for any field, it can be quite easier and faster to find a particular term in a blink of an eye. According to historical development English lexicography has a long history, evolving through stages of monolingual and bilingual dictionary creation and the origin of the language belonged to German while Uzbek language was Turkic. Uzbek lexicography, while younger, has developed significantly, particularly in the 20th century,

with a focus on bilingual dictionaries to support language learning and cultural exchange.
[5;253]

However, although people have noteworthy tools and provided research works, dictionaries, we are currently facing various challenges when tackling the translation issues and problems. Translation challenges often arise when transferring linguistic terms between languages like English and Uzbek due to differences in usage, meaning, and cultural contexts. Translating linguistic terms between English and Uzbek presents several challenges due to differences in language structure, cultural context, and the evolution of vocabulary. Now we look through each of them thoroughly:

1. Technical Language. Technical translation requires precise terminology to maintain accuracy. Differences in language structure and the absence of direct equivalents can lead to ambiguity. For instance, English technical terms may not have direct counterparts in Uzbek, necessitating the creation of new terms or explanatory phrases.

2. Lexical Gaps. Lexical gaps occur when a concept in one language lacks a direct equivalent in another. In translating between English and Uzbek, such gaps can pose significant challenges. Translators often employ strategies like borrowing, calque (loan translation), or descriptive translation to bridge these gaps. [2;45]

3. Semantic Shifts. Semantic shifts refer to changes in word meanings over time or across languages. A word in English might carry different connotations in Uzbek, leading to potential misunderstandings.

4. Cultural Nuances. Cultural differences significantly impact translation. Expressions, idioms, or references deeply rooted in one culture may not resonate or might be misinterpreted in another. [4;208]

According to these abovegiven challenges it can be evaluated some examples based on linguistic terms:

1. Specialized linguistic terms in English may have precise definitions, while their counterparts in Uzbek might have limited use or slightly altered meanings which causes the emergence of Technical Challenge. For example, in English the term 'Phonology' refers to the study of sound systems and patterns in a language. Nevertheless, in Uzbek: 'Fonologiya' is used in academic settings but might lack everyday contextual associations, limiting its use outside scientific discussions.

2. For example, the English term 'Pragmatics' studies how context influences meaning. In Uzbek: A close term 'Pragmatika' exists but isn't widely recognized outside academic circles, resulting in explanations such as "kontekst ta'siri orqali so'z ma'nosi"(contextual influence on meaning).

3. Some terms shift meaning when translated due to different language-specific interpretations which occurs Semantic Shifts. The English term 'Syntax' universally

refers to sentence structure. In Uzbek: 'Sintaksis' is interpreted similarly but may occasionally refer to broader ideas like grammatical organization, expanding its semantic range. [1; 57]

4. Terms may carry cultural associations in English that don't translate well to Uzbek which create additional burden called 'Cultural Nuances'. For instance, the English term 'Discourse analysis' involves studying language in social contexts, with frequent reference to cultural, political, and philosophical dimensions. In Uzbek: 'Nutq tahlili' carries linguistic meanings but might overlook embedded cultural nuances unless specifically elaborated. [1; 56]

In conclusion, overcoming translation challenges requires a combination of linguistic, cultural, and contextual approaches. With these problems and issues on mind, it can be gathered several effective strategies for each type of challenge. Lexicographers, specialized teachers or linguists might build glossaries of specialized terms for both languages, ensuring consistency in academic and professional contexts. Another useful way can be using descriptive translations or explanations when direct equivalents don't exist. For example: For pragmatics, explain it as "kontekst ta'siri orqali so'z ma'nosi" (contextual influence on meaning) in Uzbek until a recognized term gains wider acceptance.

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